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Quantitative methods for evaluation of anti-fouling treatments for marine energy system materials

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Abstract

Marine fouling is a widespread issue affecting nearly every natural and synthetic material within the ocean. When subjected to marine fouling and corrosion, the operating costs of marine energy systems (MES) increase due to lost efficiency, device failure, and maintenance needs. Therefore, the need to protect devices from fouling and corrosion is of critical importance to the blue economy and its supporting industries. However, developing and analyzing preventative fouling measures for MES is a complex multi-factor problem. Primarily, MES are composed of mixed materials including metals, polymers, and elastomers, which makes them highly subject to fouling and failure, and the development of a single total system anti-fouling coating unlikely. Coatings currently in use were developed primarily for the shipping and boating industry and then applied to MES materials for testing. However, the differing conditions of exposure between these systems directly affects the efficacy of anti-fouling treatments. For example, ship and boat hulls are comparably smooth, featureless, and experience extended exposures to velocities exceeding $6 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, while MES have highly variable geometries featuring curves, sharp corners, and material interfaces that are exposed to velocities below $2 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. To address these issues, we are evaluating marine anti-fouling coatings using natural, unfiltered seawater in tanks at the PNNL marine lab facility in Sequim, Washington. To alter the exposed surface, four different representative materials (aka, coupons) were either coated with commercial anti-fouling paints or treated with a new method of laser surface processing and then submerged in seawater tanks with circulating water flow and natural sunlight for a period of up to nine months. Every three months, a subset of coupons was removed from the tank and subjected to a wet/dry weighing process, a two-step protein and collagen staining process followed with imaging, and an extraction of the fouling layer for measurement of total organic carbon and nitrogen content. Wet and dry weights were compared to initial coupon weights and untreated coupons, then used to calculate a percent change in mass. The images of stained coupons were analyzed using a program designed to evaluate image pixel intensity to generate ratios for the total protein and non-acidic components in the fouling layers. Measurements of total organic carbon and nitrogen were used to calculate comparative ratios for determining biomass accumulation. When taken all together, these techniques provide a comprehensive and effective method for comparison of marine anti-fouling treatments which can be used to compare dissimilar substrate materials even when exposure conditions are biologically relevant and variable.

Keywords: marine energy systems; biofouling; anti-fouling coatings; laser surface processing; materials science

1. Introduction

Marine biofouling and corrosion are long-standing problems that affect nearly every exposed material. For marine energy systems (MES), the wear on materials increases costs due to device failure and continued maintenance. Additionally, the materials and surfaces used in wave energy converters and tidal turbines do not create equivalently smooth, streamline slipstreams found on ocean-going vessels. Instead, MES entail tight junctions, sharp edges, corners, and mixed materials that increase or accelerate the effects of corrosion and fouling. Traditional mitigation approaches for marine surfaces involves coating exposed surfaces and/or using expensive duplex stainless steel (SS). While surface coatings for boats are well characterized, it is poorly understood how anti-fouling coatings perform on MES materials, such as thermoplastics and composites. Moreover, paint coatings lack durability and need to be periodically refreshed. Here we evaluate the performance of a laser surface processing (LSP) method for corrosion prevention, as well as the performance of anti-fouling coatings applied to MES materials and tested in similar environmental conditions.

Corrosion is a big challenge for the US Department of Defense and Department of Energy [1, 2]. Estimates indicate that corrosion costs the US Navy ~\$3B per year [3]. These costs are incurred from reduced vessel efficiency as well as maintenance for cleaning and protective repainting in dry dock every 5-7 years. Laser surface processing with relatively low pulse energies has been used to locally modify the surface of materials without directly impacting bulk material properties. Previous work demonstrated that LSP was shown to inhibit salt-water induced corrosion of magnesium AZ31B alloy [4]. Therefore, we investigated the potential of LSP-induced corrosion resistance using aluminum (Al) and low-carbon steel alloys.

Antifouling coatings use many different techniques to prevent or limit biofouling. These strategies include the use of toxins (e.g., copper, zinc, E-conea™), micro or nanotextured surfaces, and various chemical modifications to control hydrophobicity, paint ablation, or zwitterionic chemistries. Most coatings require water flow across a surface to promote toxin release or gradual paint ablation. Other coatings have chemistries to prevent organisms from establishing strong adhesive bonds, therefore relying on currents to wash the organisms off the surface. Regardless of coating style, it is largely unknown how coatings perform in MES operating environments. To evaluate anti-fouling paints, the performance of coated coupons was tested in seawater tanks at the PNNL Marine and Coastal Research Laboratory.

Evaluating and comparing surface treatments and coatings is not straightforward. Traditional ASTM testing methods for antifouling materials [5, 6] require visually assessing the buildup of fouling materials on surfaces. However, the methods are highly subjective based on the expertise of the evaluator, and results are not quantifiable. To address this issue, a variety of analytical methods (weight change, staining and image analysis, determination of total organic carbon) have been employed to measure biofouling on coupons [7-11] and compare surface coatings.

Nomenclature

316L SS	316L grade stainless steel
FR4	Flame retardant glass-reinforced epoxy resin laminate
LSP	Laser surface processing
MES	Marine energy systems

2. Methodology

2.1 Preparation of coupons for laser surface processing (LSP)

Three commercial alloy metals were selected as test materials representative of those used in MES. Coupons (3" x 3") were prepared from 6061 Al (T6 temper, ~1.58 mm thick), 316L SS (~1.45 mm thick), and a low-carbon steel (1.38 mm thick). Coupons were treated with an LSP method performed using a Q-switched Nd:YAG nanosecond pulsed laser (Spectra-Physics Quanta-Ray Lab-150, $\lambda=1064$ nm), with a pulse width of 6-8 ns, every ~10 s. The setup for LSP included a water-containing workpiece atop an xyz raster stage. Individual LSP samples were treated with average laser power corresponding to values of 1.28 W, 2.34 W, and 3.12 W. Untreated samples served as the baseline. Prior to exposure in saline (laboratory) or seawater (marine lab), Peelseal Green (Maskcoat®, USA) was applied to the edges of each coupon with subsequent weighing and imaging of both sides.

2.2 Preparation of coupons with marine anti-fouling paints

Representative materials were selected for coating with marine anti-fouling coatings. Materials included aluminum (1/8" thick), 316L SS (1/8" thick), FR4 glass-reinforced epoxy resin laminate (1/8" thick), and a glass-reinforced Elium® (Arkema, USA) resin (1/4" thick). Materials were cut into three coupon sizes (1" x 1", 3" x 3", 8"

x 8") and holes were drilled in the corners to allow for mounting in seawater tanks. The aluminum, SS, and FR4 were sandblasted prior to painting, but Elium® resin coupons had a pre-roughened surface. In phase 1 of studies, aluminum coupons were pre-coated with Intergard 264 marine primer and then distributed to research institutions ((North Dakota State University (NDSU), Brigham Young University (BYU), Sandia National Laboratory (SNL)) for coating with anti-fouling paints in development (**Table 1** lists these coatings)). Coupons were submerged in tanks for a period of 30, 60, and 90 days. Ongoing studies (phase 2) investigate 316L SS, FR4, and Elium® and were coated in our own lab with commercial paints per manufacturer's instructions, prior to exposure for 3, 6, and 9 months (data not shown).

Table 1. List of coupon coatings tested in phase 1 studies.

Paint Name	Paint Style	Aluminum Coupons		
		8" x 8"	3" x 3"	1" x 1"
Primer Control	Intergard 264 primer only	12	20	38
SN1	ePaint SN1	10	6	18
Intersleek	Intersleek 900	12	6	18
NDSU 1	no information	12	6	18
NDSU 2	no information	12	6	18
NDSU 3	no information	12	6	18
NDSU 4	no information	12	6	18
NDSU 5	no information	12	6	18
BYU 1	IS731 base coat; IS970 top coat containing 1.0% CSA-120	12	6	18
BYU 2	IS731 base coat; IS970 top coat containing 2.5% CSA-120	12	6	18
SNL-MLBD1	no information	12	6	18
SNL-MLBD2	Intersleek 970 + NH3+	12	6	18
SNL-MH1	zwitterionic brush polymer	12	6	18
SNL-MH2	polydopamine + Ag nanoparticles	12	6	18
SNL-BAHS1	Ag Nanoparticles + Int 900 system	12	6	18
SNL-BAHS2	Ag Nanoparticles + Epoxy (Epon 8021)	4	2	6
SNL-EPON	Epoxy Blank (Epon 8021)	4	2	6

Aluminum coupons provided by collaborators (phase 1), and coupons painted by our lab (phase 2) were prepared as described and then mounted in either low-flow tanks (**Figure 1A**) with controlled water exchange or a higher flow, 42' long raceway tank (**Figure 1B**) with a flow velocity of ~2.5 knots maintained with propellers positioned at opposing tank ends. Coupons were mounted on PVC frames with appropriate spacing and then submerged. **Figure 1C** depicts 8" x 8" coupons mounted on a PVC frame after they were removed from the raceway tank.

Figure 1 | Anti-fouling testing in marine tanks. A. A circular low-flow, 500 gal indoor tank is depicted with aluminum coupons hanging from PVC frame. Lighting is controlled with overhead lights on a diurnal cycle. B. Raceway tank during setup. A 42' long tank with a divider down the middle allows for controlled rotational flow by positioning propellers at each end of the tank. C. Coupons on a PVC mounting frame after they were removed from the raceway tank.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Corrosion resistance and biofouling of laser surface processed coupons

LSP coupons were prepared as described and submerged in laboratory saline solution or placed in outdoor raw seawater tanks. Every month, a duplicate set of indoor, saline submerged coupons were removed and weighed to

determine formation of corrosion products, then replaced in saline. Coupons in outdoor tanks were prepared in triplicate with two sacrificial time points (3 and 6 months). **Figure 2A** depicts a clean LSP coupon with PeelSeal Green prior to submersion. In **Figure 2B**, the color change on coupon surface after 30 days in saline is evident and salt crystals are visible upon close inspection. **Figure 2C** shows a biofouled coupon after 6 months in the marine tank where biofouling is evident both on the LSP surface area and the PeelSeal Green. The plot (**Figure 2D**) depicts the calculated average weight gained per unit area (mm^2), as determined from weighing coupons (initial weight, I_w) and (final weight, F_w) before and after submersion, then dividing by the exposed surface area (A_E), and then dividing by n , number of samples. (**Equation 1**). Corrosion data for saline coupons (gray bars) indicated minimal weight change over 6 months for all samples except 1.28 W, indicating corrosion inhibition under controlled conditions. Data from the marine tank samples revealed that coupons with no LSP experienced the highest weight gain. Since saline coupons showed a minimal weight gain compared to marine tank coupons, the lab gathered data can be associated with corrosion while marine data is mostly due to biofouling. Of note, the highest energy LSP appeared to be effective at preventing fouling, but after 6 months, the other treatments were not significantly different from one another. Together these results indicate that LSP may have a protective effect on aluminum samples as the laser energy is increased during the sample treatment.

Figure 2 | The effects of LSP on marine biofouling. A. LSP coupon with PeelSeal applied to edges and string threaded through hole to facilitate hanging. B. Coupon treated with 1.28 W and submerged in saline solution, then imaged upon removal. C. Coupon treated with 1.28 W after six months submersion in marine seawater tank. D. Plot of average weight gain per unit area (mm^2) of coupons in lab (gray bars) or marine tank 3 and 6 months (maroon and cyan bars respectively). Error bars indicate the standard deviation of three replicates.

$$\text{Equation 1. } y = \left\{ \left(\frac{F_w - I_w}{F_w} \right) \div A_E \right\} \div n$$

3.2 Evaluation of anti-fouling coatings on coupons in raw seawater marine tank

Coupons removed from tanks were subjected to a series of analytical tests including percent weight change [7], analysis of total organic carbon content in the biofilm [11], and staining with biological dyes and corresponding image analysis to determine intensity of biological growth [9]. Graphical analysis was plotted according to duration of exposure with standard deviations of the value for each test. A representative summary data set of results is shown below in **Figure 3**. From the staining and image analysis of $8'' \times 8''$ coupons, the biological growth intensity

Figure 3 | Analytical results for comparison of anti-fouling coatings. A. Biological growth intensity plot as determined from biological staining and image analysis of $8'' \times 8''$ coupons. Dotted lines indicate coupons were placed in raceway flow tank (F), while solid lines are coupons kept indoors in low flow tanks (S). B. Total organic carbon content of biofilm layer on $1'' \times 1''$ coupons as plotted in ppm. C. The wet biomass weight (gram) of the fouling layer on $3'' \times 3''$ coupons when removed from the water. Tables to the side of plots indicate the values plotted for each point.

(BGI) is a derived unit (**Figure 3A**). Results indicate that the primer control and Intersleek 900 showed the highest and lowest respective BGI. Results for total organic carbon (**Figure 3B**) were determined by removing biofilm with a 3% hydrogen peroxide solution followed by analysis in a TOC analyzer. For the primer control, TOC content was higher in the flow tank than the static tank which corresponded with trends seen in the image analysis plots in **Figure 3A**. Intersleek 900 provided the best protection in all three conditions, with the exception that when placed in the raceway tank, there was an increase in biomass change over time that accumulated on the coupons. As anticipated, in all cases, the Intergard 264 primer control experienced the highest biofouling, which also served to validate our analytical methods.

4. Conclusion

Solutions to biofouling and corrosion require a multi-faceted approach. Demonstrated here is a novel laser surface processing method which has shown some protective effects against corrosion and biofouling. This method may be useful in MES for the treatment of smaller metal surfaces or tight spaces and corners where it is difficult to apply anti-fouling treatments. However, more research is needed to understand the effects of biofouling attachment mechanisms at higher laser energies. Additionally, the ability to quantitatively compare anti-fouling treatments on different materials is a valuable tool for assessing not just the efficacy of surface coatings, but for predicting maintenance and cleaning schedules for deployed MES. Future work will apply these tools to the continued study of commercial paints currently submerged in seawater tanks for the purposes of building out a knowledge database of both paints and underlying materials. As demands for marine energy solutions increase for powering the blue economy, it is only with the continued development of new tools and technologies that those demands will be met.

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